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EFFECT OF BOARD SIZE AND ITS INDEPENDENCE ON ENVIRONMENTAL REPORTING OF LISTED MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examines the effects of board size and board independence on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. It has a population of 61 manufacturing firms and a sample size of 31 firms which was arrived at based on a criterion that only listed manufacturing firms with full data over the period of the study (2009-2018) are considered. It used secondary sources of data gathering and data were extracted from content analysis of annual reports and accounts of listed manufacturing firms under studied. The data gathered were analyzed using multiple regression technique; also, diagnostic test such as normality, multicollinearity, and Hausman specification were conducted on the data used. The study found that board independence has a significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria; while board size has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Based on this finding, the study recommends that, listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria should have more independent directors on their board as their decisions will always favour firm's existence. Also, firms should have environmental committee, which will help them identify the need of their host environment.

Keywords: *environmental disclosure index, diagnostic test, multiple regression, board size, manufacturing firms*

1. Introduction

Global economic developments are usually characterized by environmental activities that result in problems such as growing pollution, global warming, deforestation, desertification, uncontrolled dumping of waste materials among others. These developments have increased the pressure on firms from stakeholders to disclose their efforts towards protecting the earth and its resources. Environmental reporting involves release of information on the impact of organization's activities on the natural environment and such activities include, waste management, recycling, carbon management, emission and pollution management, tree planting and wildlife conservation among others (Uyagu, 2019). Environmental reporting can be described as the public disclosure of information concerning an entity's environmental activities to particular interest groups within society and to the society at large. Environmental reporting has become a major component of today's business activities because of increased stakeholder's awareness of the damaging effects of environmental activities in the areas where listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria operate.

The decision whether a firm engages in environmental reporting or not can be influenced by a lot of board characteristics, such as board size, board independence, CEO duality, ownership concentration, board meeting among others. However, this study focused on board size and board independence in order to examine their effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Board size and independence are critical components of board's decision-making tools that may affect either positively or negatively the level of environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. For an example, Victor and Fodio (2012) opined that, the higher the board size, the higher the level of environmental reporting and vice versa. Similarly, the higher

the number of the non-executive directors on the board, the higher the level of environmental reporting and vice versa. In examining above statement, a board with large size may have the opportunity to make a robust decision, because of opportunity to garner different ideas from members on board, which may influence the level of environmental reporting. Also, a board dominated by non-executive directors may report more environmental activities, as a result of more controls that will be infused on the board decision-making process by the presence of non-executive directors and vice versa. The board size and independence as a top management tools, act as a catalyst in formulating policies and strategies to be followed by managers and it has been argued that a greater number of directors on the board mixed with independent directors may reduce the likelihood of information asymmetry (Chen & Jaggi, 2000).

However, there exist distinct problems with corporate environmental reporting; it is unfortunate that irrespective of corporate governance in place, manufacturing firms in Nigeria have left trail of woes in their path with so much damage and problems to human life in the environment where they operate; such as air and water pollution, habitat destruction, land degradation among others. In Nigeria, environmental reporting seems to be at its lowest ebb, due to ineffectiveness of board size and independence (Ashafoke & Ilaboya, 2017). Also, over the years despite wide acknowledgement by stakeholders of the importance of corporate environmental reporting, there are no standards for comparison, as environmental reporting remains voluntary within and across countries (Horvath et al., 2017). It is also likely that in most developing countries, such as Nigeria, the weakness in environmental reporting may be attributed to the weakness arising from the functions of board size and independence (Mgbame & Onosaye, 2015).

Manufacturing firms are sensitive environmental businesses that have a profound effect on the environment in the course of carrying out its activities. More so, Nigeria is chosen because, being a developing nation, due prominence might not have been given to environmental reporting in Manufacturing firms annual report. As regards environmental reporting, different organizations such as the chemical manufacturing association of Nigeria have issued guidelines, but these guidelines are only advisory in nature and not mandatory. Consequently, the researcher's interest is therefore to know the extent to which board size and independence have influenced the voluntary environmental reporting in Nigeria listed manufacturing firms. In order to achieve this, the following hypotheses were developed and tested.

Ho: board size has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Ho: board independence has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

This section examines the relevant literatures connected to the study from conceptual, empirical and theoretical perspectives. Also, several issues on board size and its independence in relation to environmental reporting will be reviewed.

2.1 Conceptual Review

Gray et al. (1995) define corporate environmental reporting as the process of communicating the environmental effects of organizations' economic action to particular interest groups within society and to society at large, there by influencing the public's perception towards their operations. Also, Aburaya (2012) defines environmental reporting as the set of information items that relate to a firm's past, current and future environmental management activities and

performance. Campbell (2014) simply defines environmental reporting as the reporting pertaining to the impact an organizational process or operation may have on the natural environment. Furthermore, Gray et al. (1995) opine that firms use their environmental reports to construct themselves and their relationships with the stakeholders as they strive to create and maintain the conditions for their continued profitability and growth. Uyagu et al. (2018) equally opine that environmental reporting can legitimize corporate power by meeting the expectations of the society where listed manufacturing firms operate. In addition, the information contained in environmental reports are necessary for accountability, comparability and probity, hence, when not made available could be held synonymously with being bias, not transparent, fraudulent and liable to risk which in turn could dissuade patronages from customers, suppliers, investors and surrounding communities.

Though, in Nigeria, environmental reporting issues remain voluntary in line with global best practices, but some countries like Finland and Sweden have made it compulsory. The voluntary nature is due to lack of uniform standard regulatory environmental reporting on a global scale. An examination of International Accounting Standards (IAS) and International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) indicate that no international standard is exclusively dedicated to the provisions of such information, but there are numerous direct and indirect remarks on the issue of environmental accounting on the different accounting standards (Goyal, 2013). Therefore, in this study, the most widely known International Standards for assessing environmental activity of manufacturing firms known as International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 14031 will be adopted. It contains disclosure requirements which provide voluntary standards of environmental reporting.

Conceptually, board size is defined as the number of members on the board (Jensen, 1993; Yermack, 1996). Board size may influence the level of environmental reporting because the level of reporting is a strategic decision made by the board members, moreover, the size of the board is believed to affect the ability of the board to monitor and evaluate management which may affect the level of environmental reporting (Zahra, 2000). Patrick et al. (2015) emphasized that board size has a strong effect on the level of environmental reporting. He buttressed his assertion from the perspective of agency theory, it can be argued that agency problems are easier tackled by larger boards because of the presence of greater number of people evaluating and observing management decisions, while reverse is the case of smaller boards. Therefore, it suffices to assert that larger boards have the capability to commit less time and effort in managing the firm's activities, while smaller boards may commit more effort and time in overseeing the activities of the management. Furthermore, it can be said that board monitoring is done more effectively by larger boards due to the inherent ability to share the responsibility amidst a larger board. Yu (2018) acknowledged that larger boards can serve as a catalyst for more environmental disclosure.

Daton et al. (1998) defines board independence as the proportion of executive directors to non-executive directors on the board. He opined that an effective board should comprise of majority of non-executive directors. In corporate governance literature, independent directors are directors that do not engage in day-to-day management of the organization. And independent director is one that is free from the control of the chief executive (Peasnell et al., 2000). In the opinion of Oba (2014), board independence has a significant negative effect on financial reporting quality, which means that the existence of more independent directors does not guarantee timeliness of financial reporting. Even though, it was said by Dalton (1998) that the presence of non-executive directors will affect positively the level of environmental reporting, but from the view held by Oba (2014), it is discovered that the presence of non-executive directors on the board

may not guarantee effective environmental reporting. This is because, the ineffectiveness of non-executive directors on the board, may arise from the inability of them to influence significantly board decisions on environmental reporting.

2.2 Empirical Review

This section reviews related literature on the study. Halil (2016) examines the effect of board characteristics on environmental disclosure: Evidence from Turkish listed firms. The study examines 62 non-financial firms listed on Turkish Stock Exchange. The scope of the study is firms listed on B1st – 100 index in the financial year 2011. The secondary data and ordinary least regression model were used to analyze the effect of board size on environmental reporting. The finding is that firms with larger boards disclose more environmental information than firms with smaller boards, because larger boards can make robust decisions that will encourage more environmental reporting. Similarly, Victor and Fodio (2012) examine the effect of board size on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study covers the period of 2005-2009. The study uses secondary data and logistic regression with the aid of SPSS to analyze the data. The finding is that, board size has negative significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

In like manner, Eyenubo (2013) examines the effect of board size on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study period is 2001-2010. The sample of the study is 50 firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study uses secondary data and regression to analyze and establish the effect of board size on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The finding is that, bigger board size has a negative significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Also, Mgbame and Onoyase (2015) examine the effect of board size on the extent of environmental reporting in Nigeria Oil Industry. The scope of the study is 2010-2013. A sample of 15 listed firms in Nigeria was selected for the study. The study uses secondary data and multiple regression to analyze data. The finding is, board size has positive significant effect on environmental reporting.

Based on the concept of expert power, it could be argued that, the larger the board size the more diverse the experiences and opinions and the better the supervisory capacity of the board with attendant consequences of improved environmental reporting. Lonel-Alin (2012) examines the relationship between environmental reporting and corporate governance characteristics of 50 Romanian listed firms. He uses secondary data and regression model with aid of SPSS to analyze the data and the relationship between variables. The finding is, the presence of independent directors on the board helps to reduce the conflict of interest between the stakeholders and the company management which invariably leads to increase in environmental reporting. Mohammed et al. (2017) examine board independence and environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Pakistan. The study uses secondary data and multiple regression to establish the effect of increase in the number of independent directors on the level of environmental reporting. The finding is, the increase in the number of independent directors will increase the level of environmental reporting in the annual reports of the Hong Kong.

Chen and Jaggi (2002) examine the effect of board independence on corporate reporting, using a sample of 68 listed manufacturing firms for the period 1996-2000, which was analyzed using ordinary least square regression. They found a positive significant effect of board independence on environmental reporting. Their findings are consistent with agency theory tenets where a higher proportion of independent directors enhance voluntary financial reporting. Aktaruddin et al. (2011) investigated board independence and voluntary disclosure in corporate

annual reports of Malaysian listed firms. A total of 96 firms were sampled and were analyzed using regression. The findings reveal that there is positive significant effect of board independence on the level of environmental reporting among Malaysian listed firms and that firms can expect more voluntary disclosure with the inclusion of a larger number of non-executive directors on the board. In the light of above, it is suggestive that board independence has a positive significant effect on the level of environmental reporting. This may be as a result of each independent directors coming on board with his or her vast experience and this can go a long way in enhancing relevant information to be reported – therefore, the higher the number of independent directors, the higher the volume of environmental information reported.

In this study, a corporate attribute of firm size is used as control variable as previously done by (Aburaya, 2012; Akbas, 2016). This study considers firm size, because, it is expected that the size of a firm should impact either negatively or positively the level of environmental reporting. Cooper and Zainudin (2009) analyze the scope, quality and medium of reporting on environmental matters for 2005 using a sample of 315 listed firms drawn from nine countries. The factors examined include country's economic development, country's accounting system and firm size. The finding is, firm size has no significant effect on environmental reporting. However, in Galani et al., (2011), it was found that firm size has positive significant effect on environmental reporting.

In Nigeria, several authors such as (Haslinda et al., 2015; Ashafoke & Ilaboya, 2017; Mgbame & Onoyase, 2015) have examined the effect of board size and independence on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms using either three or four years as their study period, but this study has examined the effect of board size and independence on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria using ten years (2009-2018) as its study period. This approach was adopted to allow for a wider coverage, which can give birth to robust findings.

2.3 Theoretical Review

Different theoretical approaches have been used to explain environmental reporting of firms. Two of such theories which affect environmental reporting by listed manufacturing firms are: Agency theory and legitimacy theory. These theories can be classified as system-oriented theories that view firms as being part of a broader social system (Deegan, 2001). Within a system-based perspective, Deegan (2001) argues that companies are influenced by the society in which they operate because they are part of the system. This means that environmental reporting concerning the society is considered to constitute a strategy to influence corporate relationships with other parties with which it interacts.

Agency theory has been used by researchers in an effort to explain the control put in place by the investors to alleviate a perceived information asymmetry. According to Aburaya (2012), a simple agency model suggests that, as a result of information asymmetry and self-satisfaction, principals lack reasons, to trust their agents and will seek to resolve these concerns by putting in place controls to align the interests of agents with those of principals so as to reduce the scope for information disproportionate and opportunistic behaviours of managers. Furthermore, in order to avoid a breach of action by the manager against the shareholders, strict control and monitoring are needed to ensure that their (managers) efforts are focused on maximizing the shareholders' wealth; and maximization of shareholders' wealth can be achieved via adequate environmental reporting (Uyagu, 2019). Therefore, appropriate corporate governance mechanisms such as, board size and board independence have been introduced to control agency problems and to ensure that managers act in the best interest of their shareholders;

Legitimacy theory exists when there is agreement between the expectations of the society and operations of the organization (Gray et al., 1995). Uwalomwa and Udiale (2011) in their study assert that the explanation for this trend is not unconnected with business organizations' desire to create, maintain or repair their societal legitimacy. The legitimacy theory argues that firms will offer information bordering around its activities to society including environmental information. According to O' Donovan (2002), this could better be done by using environmental reporting so as to gain a reputable image and acknowledgement by society. Many empirical studies indicate that firms legitimize their activities because corporate management reacts to community expectations (Ashafoke & Ilaboya, 2017; Demb & Neubaur, 2018; Halil, 2016). The legitimacy theory provides a comprehensive view point on corporate environmental reporting as it clearly recognizes that organizations are bound by the social contract in which they agree to perform various socially desired actions in return for approval of their objectives, which guarantees their continued existence and their successful operations. From the foregoing theoretical review, legitimacy theory suggests a nexus between corporate environmental reporting and community concerns so that management must react to community expectations and changes. Therefore, this study is anchoring on agency theory as one of the theories adopted because it resolves conflicts of interest between the principal (shareholders) and agents (management) on environmental issues.

3. Methodology

This study used ex-post facto design to enable the researcher examine the effect of board size and board independence on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The population of the study is all the sixty-one (61) listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria operating and trading on the floor of Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) as at 31st December, 2018 from which a sample of thirty-one (31) firms that have full data over the period of the study (2009-2018) was drawn. The selection of sample was based on those firms whose annual reports for the period (2009-2018) were available. Using judgement sampling, thirty (30) firms out of sixty-one (61) were dropped, because of incomplete annual reports or delisting from Nigerian stock exchange. The remaining thirty-one (31) members served as the samples for the study. The choice arises due to the fact that they are readily available, accessible and also provides a greater potential for comparability of results. The annual reports of the selected listed firms for the time period 2009-2018 were used and STATA 14 was used to run the regression.

The independent variables are board size and board independence. Board size (BS) is measured as total number of both executive and non-executive members on board. Whereas, board independence is measured as the proportion of non-executive directors on board to total number of members on board at year end. The study consists of one dependent variable known as environmental reporting. The measurement of the dependent variable is thus, a checklist using ISO 14031 where coding mechanism is used as seen in Wiseman (1982) and Uyagu (2019). The ISO14031 contains sixty checklists. See appendix II. The study contains a control variable of firm size (FS). This is because, it is consistently found to be related to level an extent of reporting (Campbell, 2004; Cormier & Magnan, 2003; & Wilmhurst & Frost, 2000).

Table 1 presents the variables and their measurements together with the related literature

Table 1
Variables Definition and Measurement

Variables	Definition	Measurement	Sources
Independent Variables			
BS	Board size	Total number of members on the board at year end	Victor & Fodio (2012); Eneyubo (2013); Ashafoke & Ilaboya (2017), Uyagu (2019)
BI	Board independence	Non-executive directors/number of members on the board at year end	Aburaya (2012); Halil (2016); Mgbame & Onoyase (2015); Uyagu (2019)
Control Variable			
FS	Firm size	Log of total assets at year end	Salama (2003); Garcia – Ayuso & Larrinaga (2003); Mohammed & Tamoi (2006)
Dependent Variable			
ER	Environmental reporting	Unweighted disclosure approach and a firm is scored “1” for an item disclosure in the annual report and “0” if not disclosed	Uyagu (2019); Wiseman (1982); Deegan (1998); Hassan (2010); Toms (2002); Uwuigbe (2013); Yahaya (2018)

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For the purpose of finding the strength of the effect of board size and board independence as independent variables on environmental reporting as dependent variable, multiple regression model is adopted as shown below in a functional manner.

Model

$$ER = f(\text{B size, B Ind, F size}) \quad (1)$$

This can be written mathematically as

$$ER_{it} = a + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 FS_{it} + \varepsilon \dots \quad (2)$$

Whereas;

BS = Board size

BI = Board independence

FS = Firm size

ER = Environmental reporting

ε = constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = model parameters or linear regression coefficients

ε = the error term used in the regression model

i = number of observations

t = time period

The study performed diagnostic test such as normality test, multi-co-linearity test, omitted bias test and Hausman specification test and panel effect test for reliability and validity.

4. Discussion of findings

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Observations	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
ER	310	0.239	0.109	0.000	0.450
BS	310	9.110	2.335	5.000	17.000
BI	310	0.669	0.200	0.083	1.000
FS	310	9.240	2.212	4.230	14.240

Source: STATA 14 Output (2020)

Table 2 shows that environmental reporting (ER) of the selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria has mean value of 23.9 with standard deviation of 10.9 with minimum and maximum value of 0 and 45 respectively. This implies that on average, 23.9 of environmental reporting is being disclosed by the manufacturing firms in Nigeria and minimum level is 0, while the maximum level is 45. This means with the combined efforts of the selected listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria to report environmental issues, the maximum level of reporting is 45. The average board size of the selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria is approximately 9 with standard deviation of 2.34. The dispersion is due to the difference in number of board members of the selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This is because large firms have high number of board members while smaller firms have few board members as it will save them cost. The result also shows that on the average listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria have at least 9 board members. The least board size of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria is 5 members; this complies with the corporate governance code that recommends minimum of 5 members on the board; while the maximum of 17 board members exceeds the 15-maximum recommended by the corporate governance code. The average board independence is 66.9 with standard deviation of 20.0 with minimum and maximum value of 8.3 and 100 respectively. The result shows that there is a wide dispersion between the mean of the number of board independence and each variable of the data. The dispersion is due to the difference in number of board independence of the selected listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The control variable firm size has mean of 9.24 and standard deviation of 2.21 with minimum and maximum value of 4.23 and 14.24 respectively. The analysis of the description statistics of the studied variables shows the nature and the extent of dispersion data, which the wide dispersion between the mean and the standard deviation of the variables strongly shows that the data did not follow the normal curve.

Data normality test was conducted and the result shows that the data does not follow normal distribution, this is due to the fact that the P-values of the Z-statistics are statistically significant at 99% confidence interval (1% level of significant). The normality assumption failure of the data means that the models require a more generalized estimate. Multicollinearity test shows that the variables are not suffering from multi collinearity since the variance inflation factors (VIF) are less than 5 and the tolerance level is also within the acceptable range of 1. This implies that the independent variables are appropriate and well fit into the model.

The Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test shows that there is panel effect among the variables with P-value less than 0.05 level of significant at 95% confidence interval. Hausman specification test shows that the model is statistically not significant with probability 0.071, which implies that a random effect model will be run on the model.

Table 3

<i>Regression Result</i>			
Variables	Model (ER) (Robust RE) (GLS)		
	Coefficients	z-value	P-value
Constant	0.151	3.50	0.000
BS	0.001	0.43	0.669
BI	0.061	1.93	0.054
FS	0.004	0.99	0.320
R ²	0.227		
Wald chi2	5.270		
P-value			0.153

Source: STATA 14 Output

The regression results as shown in table 3 reveals that the R-squared which is often referred to as coefficient of determination of the variables for model (Environmental reporting) was found to be 0.227. This implies that 22.7% of the changes in environmental reporting can be explained by the independent variables combined (board size, board independence and the control variable: firm size). This is also confirmed by the Wald Chi² statistics of 5.27 whose probability (0.153) implies that the independent variables combined are not good predictors of environmental information (they are statistically not significant). The results also show that board size, board independence and the control variable; firm size has positive effect on environmental reporting with their coefficients 0.001, 0.061 and 0.004 respectively, though board independence is significant at 0.054 at 95% confidence interval, while board size and firm size are not statistically significant, because, their probabilities are 0.669 and 0.320 which are greater than 0.05 significant level at 95% confidence interval. It then means when board independence increases by 1%, environmental reporting will increase by 5.4%. The result shows that the null hypothesis two that says board independence does not have significant effect on environmental reporting does not hold water and must be rejected.

The findings show that regression result for the model has a positive coefficient and insignificant effect for board size, which confirms the hypothesis that says, board size has no significant effect on environmental reporting. The finding agrees with Victor and Fodio (2012); and Eyenubo (2013) who found a positive and insignificant effect of board size on environmental reporting. However, the finding disagrees with Ashafoke and Illaboya (2017); Mgbame and Onayase (2015) who found a positive and significant effect of board size on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Also, the finding shows that the model has a positive coefficient and no significant effect on board independence, which confirms the hypothesis that says, board independence has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The finding is in disagreement with Uwuigbe (2013); Akbas (2016) and Brown and Marshall (2011) who found a positive and insignificant effect of board independence on environmental reporting of listed firms. However, it is in agreement with the findings of Aktaruddin et al. (2011); Hong Kong, Chen and Jaggi (2002) and Mohammed et al.

(2017) who found a positive and significant effect of board independence on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The regression result for the model shows a positive coefficient and insignificant effect for firm size, the finding is in support of Cooper and Zainudin (2009) who found a positive and insignificant effect of firm size and environmental reporting.

The reasons for the insignificant effect could be as a result of lackadaisical attitude towards the implementation of board's decisions regarding the report of environmental issues. Also, in Nigeria, there is no regulatory body to enforce environmental reporting, therefore, board members irrespective of their size and independence may not be able to affect significantly environmental reporting. Therefore, the implication of this result on policy making is that, the management of listed manufacturing firms needs to review policies around adherence to corporate governance code of board size and board independence. More so, are there stringent policies that can drive in the efforts of board size and board independence in enhancing environmental reporting? This question is imperative, because, absence of stringent policies could truncate the meaningful effect that board size and board independence could have on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The finding has negated the legitimacy theory used for this study. This is because, according to Gray et al. (1995), legitimacy theory exists when there is agreement between the expectations of the society and operations of the society. In this case, the insignificant effect of board size and independence on environmental reporting, is an indication that the expectation of the stakeholders and the society at large in regards to environmental reporting in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria is yet to be met. This is because, the a priori expectation is that board size and board independence should enhance the level of environmental reporting which will boost the morale and expectation of the stakeholders and the society at large.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examines the effect of board size and board independence on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that board independence has significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, while board size has no significant effect on environmental reporting. Also, it concludes that the level of commitment of board size to environmental reporting in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, is quite insufficient and this might be part of the reasons why environmental reporting has been low in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, but board independence is an important factor that can enhance ER of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This is because independent directors have the ability to monitor and control the extremes of the executive directors thereby protecting the interest of the shareholders and other stakeholders. In addition, the unstable institutions, weak legal environment and lack of environmental reporting standards are a contributor to unconcerned approach exhibited by corporate entities toward the natural habitat. Also, it is concluded that, the absence of regulatory body to enforce environmental reporting could jeopardize the impact that board size and board independence could have on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Based on the findings, the study recommends that since board independence has significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, therefore, listed firms should have more independent directors on their board as their decisions will always favour firm's existence. Furthermore, a better enhanced medium of communicating corporate activities within the environment should be devised by regulators of businesses in Nigeria. For example, the implementation of integrated reporting should be made compulsory. Also, from a regulatory

perspective there is presently no local standard in Nigeria for companies to prepare and publish environmental reporting. Therefore, financial reporting council of Nigeria (FRCN) should no longer allow environmental reporting to be voluntary but make it compulsory using ISO 14031 reporting guideline as a common standard of reporting among the management of manufacturing firms in Nigeria; for the purpose of attaining detailed environmental reporting and easy comparison of such reporting among firms. Finally, firms should have environmental committee, which will help them identify the need of their host communities, with regards to environmental issues.

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